

Supporting Information

Stereoselective α -deuteration of serine, cysteine, selenocysteine and 2,3-diaminopropanoic acid derivatives

Claudio D. Navo,^{§*} Paula Oroz,[#] Nuria Mazo,[#] Marina Blanco,[#] Jesús M. Peregrina[#] and Gonzalo Jiménez-Osés^{§,‡*}

[§] Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC bioGUNE), Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Bizkaia Technology Park, Building 801A, 48160 Derio, Spain.

[#] Departamento de Química, Centro de Investigación en Síntesis Química, Universidad de La Rioja, 26006 Logroño, La Rioja, Spain.

[‡] Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48013 Bilbao, Spain.

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1. Supplementary schemes and figures

Scheme S1. Diastereoselective base-promoted HDE on bicyclic serine derivative **1** and hetero-Michael addition and α -deuteration reactions of bicyclic dehydroalanine derivative **4**.

Scheme S2. Diastereoselective hydrogen-deuterium exchange (HDE) reaction on bicyclic D-serine (**ent-1**) equivalent followed by acidic hydrolysis. Yields obtained after purification of the products are shown in black. Isotopic enrichments are shown in green and in brackets.

Scheme S3. Orthogonal protection of L-serine-2-d (**3**) and solid phase synthesis of deuterated analogues of peptide **myr-Src**. Yields obtained after purification of the products are shown in black. Isotopic enrichments are shown in green and in brackets.

Scheme S4. Stereoselective synthesis of L-cysteine-2-d (**ent-6b**) by a tandem Michael addition-deuteration reaction followed by acidic hydrolysis. Isolated global yields (2 steps) determined after purification are given in black. Isotopic enrichments are shown in green and in brackets.

Scheme S5. Stereoselective synthesis of α -deuterium DAP derivative **ent-6f** by a tandem Michael addition-deuteration reaction followed by acidic hydrolysis. Isolated global yields (2 steps) determined after purification are given in black. Isotopic enrichments are shown in green and in brackets.

Figure S1. Comparison of ^1H NMR spectra for compounds **1** and **2**. Signal corresponding to H^3 , which disappears in compound **2**, is highlighted in green.

Figure S2. Comparison of ¹H NMR spectra for compounds **5a** and its unlabeled analog **5^Ha**. Signal corresponding to H α , which disappears in compound **5a**, is highlighted in green.

2. Experimental procedures

Reagents and general methods. Commercial reagents were used without further purification. Solvents were dried and redistilled prior to use in the usual way. All the reactions were carried out in oven dried glassware with magnetic stirring. Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on Macherey-Nagel precoated aluminum sheets with a 0.20 mm thickness of silica gel 60 with fluorescent indicator UV254. TLC plates were visualized with UV light and by staining with a potassium permanganate solution (0.75 g KMnO₄, 5 g K₂CO₃, and 0.63 mL 10% NaOH in 100 mL water), a ninhydrin solution (1.5 g ninhydrin in 100 mL *n*-butanol and 3.0 mL acetic acid), or a Hanessian solution (0.5 g ceric sulfate, 12 g ammonium molybdate, and 15 mL concentrated H₂SO₄ in 235 mL water). Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (230–400 mesh). Melting points were determined on a Büchi B-545. Optical rotation angles were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 341 polarimeter, using a sodium lamp ($\lambda = 589$ nm) at 25 °C in 1.0 dm long cells (0.35 or 1.0 mL). ¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectra were measured with a Bruker Avance-400 and Bruker ARX-300 spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard. Multiplicities are quoted as singlet (s), broad singlet (br s), doublet (d), doublet of doublets (dd), triplet (t), or multiplet (m). Spectra were assigned using COSY and HSQC experiments. All NMR chemical shifts (δ) were recorded in ppm and coupling constants (*J*) were reported in hertz (Hz). The results of these experiments were processed with MestreNova software. High resolution electrospray mass (ESI) spectra were recorded on a microTOF spectrometer; accurate mass measurements were achieved by using sodium formate as an external reference.

NMR Experiments. NMR experiments were performed on a 400 MHz spectrometer at 298 K. Magnitude-mode ge-2D COSY spectra were acquired with gradients by using the *cosygpqf* pulse program with a pulse width of 90°. Phase-sensitive ge-2D HSQC spectra were acquired by using *z*-filter and selection before *t*₁ removing the decoupling during acquisition by use of the *invigpndph* pulse program with CNST2 (JHC)=145. Phase-sensitive ge-2D NOESY experiments were performed using a mixing time of 800 ms. NOE intensities were normalized with respect to the diagonal peak at zero mixing time.

Deuterium incorporation quantification. The ratio of incorporated deuterium was determined by the decrease of ¹H NMR integral intensities for the specific peaks using non-exchangeable hydrogen signals as references.

Optimization of diastereoselective hydrogen-deuterium exchange reaction. Compound **1** (25 mg, 0.10 mmol) was dissolved in the corresponding solvent (or solvent mixture) under Ar atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. The mixture was cooled down to -78 °C in an acetone bath and the base and additives, if any, were then added (Table S1). After stirring for the corresponding reaction time, the quencher was added and the mixture was warmed up to room temperature, diluted with diethyl ether and extracted twice with more diethylether. The organic layers were collected, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was removed under vacuum. The crude mixture was dissolved in CDCl₃ and analyzed by ¹H NMR to determine the isotopic enrichment (%) and the relative amount of side products (**8** or **9**).

Table S1. Optimization of the diastereoselective base-promoted HDE on bicyclic serine derivative **1**.

Entry	Solvent (mL)	Base, additives (equiv.)	Reaction time (s)	Quencher	Isotopic enrichment, 2 (%) ^a	7 (%)	8 (%)
1	THF (0.5) + MeOD (0.5)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	0	0	0
2	THF (0.5) + MeOD (0.5)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	Sat. NH ₄ Cl in H ₂ O	0	0	0
3	THF (2.5) + MeOD (2.5)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	0	0	0
4	THF (2.5) + MeOD (2.5)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	Sat. NH ₄ Cl in H ₂ O	0	0	0
5	THF (5.0) + MeOD (5.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	0	0	0
6	THF (5.0) + MeOD (5.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	sat. NH ₄ Cl in H ₂ O	0	0	0
7	THF (0.5) + ⁱ PrOD (0.5)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	0	0	0
8	THF (1.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	7	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	90	0	17
9	THF (1.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	CD ₃ OD (20 equiv.)	85	0	30
10	THF (2.0)	LHMDS (4.0)	≤ 30	CD ₃ OD (50 equiv.)	37	23	40
11	THF (1.0)	KHMDS (2.0)	60	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	n. d.	100	0
12	THF (1.0)	LHMDS (2.0) + HMPA (4.0)	60	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	n. d.	60	40
13	THF (2.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	90	0	21
14	THF (2.0)	LHMDS (4.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	15	0	0
15	THF (5.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	≤ 30	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	0	0	0
16	THF (5.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	180	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	40	0	60
17	Toluene (2.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	5	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	30	0	20
18	CH ₂ Cl ₂ (2.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	5	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	60	10	17
19	Et ₂ O (2.0)	LHMDS (2.0)	5	2 M ND ₄ Cl in D ₂ O	≥ 95	0	0

^aIsotopic enrichment was determined by the relative integration of the signal corresponding to the exchanged atom (i. e. 0 = no exchange, 100 = complete exchange). n. d.: not determined due to complete decomposition. ^bCD₃OD was added to the mixture and stirred for 5 min at -78 °C in an acetone bath. Then, the mixture was warmed up to room temperature, the solvent was removed under vacuum and the crude mixture was dissolved in CDCl₃ and analyzed by ¹H NMR.

Synthesis of previously reported reagents.

Compound **1** was prepared according to the procedure described in ref. 32 of the manuscript: Aydillo, C.; Jiménez-Osés, G.; Busto, J. H.; Peregrina, J. M.; Zurbano, M. M.; Avenoza, A. Theoretical Evidence for Pyramidalized Bicyclic Serine Enolates in Highly Diastereoselective Alkylations. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2007**, *13*, 4840. Physical data are in agreement with those previously reported. ¹H NMR spectrum is provided for purity documentation:

Compound **4** was prepared according to the procedure described in ref. 34 of the manuscript: Gutiérrez-Jiménez, M. I.; Aydillo, C.; Navo, C. D.; Avenzoza, A.; Corzana, F.; Jiménez-Osés, G.; Zurbano, M. M.; Busto, J. H.; Peregrina, J. M. Bifunctional Chiral Dehydroalanines for Peptide Coupling and Stereoselective S-Michael Addition. *Org. Lett.* **2016**, 18, 2796. Physical data are in agreement with those previously reported. ¹H NMR spectrum is provided for purity documentation:

General procedure for diastereoselective hydrogen-deuterium exchange reaction. Chiral bicyclic serine derivative **1** or **ent-1** (**0.50 mmol**, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in dry diethyl ether (final concentration 50 mM) in a Schlenk under Ar atmosphere. Then, the mixture was cooled down to -78 °C **in an acetone bath** and a 1 M solution of LHMDS in THF (**1.00 mmol**, 2.0 equiv.) was added with a syringe. After stirring for 10 s, a 2 M solution of ammonium-*d*₄ chloride (ND₄Cl) in deuterium oxide (D₂O) and the mixture was warmed up to room temperature and vigorously stirred. The crude mixture was diluted with diethyl ether and the aqueous layer was extracted with more diethyl ether. The organic layers were combined, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under vacuum. The crude mixture was purified by column chromatography (7:3, hexanes/ethyl acetate) on silica gel to afford deuterated compounds **2** or **ent-2**.

General procedure for the tandem S-Michael addition and deuteration reaction. Chiral bicyclic Dha **4** or **ent-4** (**0.25 mmol**, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in a 9:1 mixture of 2-propanol-OD (*i*PrOD) and anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (final concentration 0.1 M) in a Schlenk under Ar atmosphere. Then, the corresponding thiol (**0.25 mmol**, 1.0 equiv.) and TEA (**0.25 mmol**, 1.0 equiv.) were added, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC (7:3, hexanes/ethyl

acetate. R_f (**4**) = 0.75) and, once completed, the solution was dried under vacuum. The crude mixture was analyzed by NMR and, if needed, purified by column chromatography on silica gel to afford deuterated adducts **5a-e**, **ent-5b** and **ent-5m**.

General procedure for the tandem *N*-Michael addition and deuteration reaction. Chiral bicyclic Dha **4** or **ent-4** (0.20 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in a 9:1 mixture of 2-propanol-OD (³PrOD) and anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (final concentration 0.1 M) in a Schlenk under Ar atmosphere. Then, the corresponding amine (0.20 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC (7:3, hexanes/ethyl acetate. R_f (**4**) = 0.75) and once completed, the solution was dried under vacuum to afford deuterated adducts **5f-j**, and **ent-5f**, which were used without further purification.

General procedure for the tandem *Se*-Michael addition and deuteration reaction. Sodium borodeuteride (0.23 mmol, 2.3 equiv.) was added to a solution of the corresponding diselenide (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in ethanol-OD (0.1 M) in a Schlenk under an Ar atmosphere. The mixture was stirred until it became colourless and cooled down to 0 °C in an ice bath, and acetic acid-*d*₄ (0.34 mmol, 3.4 equiv.) was then added with a syringe. A solution of **ent-4** (0.14 mmol, 1.4 equiv.) in a 1:2 mixture of dried dichloromethane and ethanol-OD (0.3 M) was added, and the reaction mixture (final concentration of the limiting reactant 0.1 M) was stirred at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC (7:3, hexanes/ethyl acetate. R_f (**4**) = 0.75) and, once completed, the solution was dried under vacuum. The crude mixture was purified by column chromatography (8:2, hexanes/ethyl acetate) on silica gel to afford deuterated adducts **ent-5k** and **ent-5l**.

General procedure for hydrolysis. Compounds **2** and **ent-2**, as well as *S*-Michael adducts **5a-e**, **ent-5b** and **ent-5m** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) were suspended in an aqueous 6 M HCl solution (final concentration 25 mM) and refluxed in an oil bath for 16 h. *N*-Michael adducts **5f-j** and **ent-5f**, as well as *Se*-Michael adducts **ent-5k** and **ent-5l** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) were suspended in an aqueous 6 M HCl solution (final concentration 25 mM) and the mixture was stirred at 60 °C in an oil bath for 16 h. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the crude mixture was redissolved in water and washed with ethyl acetate. The aqueous phase was concentrated, and the crude mixture was purified by solid phase extraction in a C18 cartridge to afford the α -deuterated amino acid derivatives **6a-j**, **ent-6b**, **ent-6f**, and **ent-6k-m**.

Solid-phase peptide synthesis. All peptides were synthesized by a stepwise microwave-assisted solid-phase peptide synthesis (MW-SPPS) on a Liberty Blue equipment, using the Fmoc strategy on Rink Amide MBHA resin (0.05 mmol). The deuterated amino acid building block (1.5 equiv) and myristic acid (1.5 equiv) were manually coupled using (2-(1*H*-benzotriazol-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethyluronium hexafluorophosphate and *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (HBTU/DIEA), while the other Fmoc-protected amino acids (5.0 equiv) were automatically coupled using oxyma pure and *N,N*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC). The peptides were then cleaved from the resin, and all acid sensitive side-chain protecting groups were simultaneously removed using trifluoroacetic acid 95% (TFA), triisopropylsilane (TIS) 2.5%, H₂O 2.5%, followed by precipitation with cold diethyl ether. Finally, all peptides were purified by semi-preparative HPLC using a Phenomenex Luna C18(2) column (10 μ m, 250 mm \times 21.2 mm) and a dual absorbance detector, with a flow rate of 20 mL/min.

Analytical HPLC was performed with a Phenomenex Jupiter C4 column (5 μm , 250 mm \times 4.60 mm) and a diode array detector, with a flow rate of 1 mL/min.

Degradation studies in human plasma. Degradation studies were performed using commercially available serum from human male AB plasma. First, 20 mM stock solutions (PBS, 100 mM, pH 7.6) of carbocysteine and carbocysteine-2-*d* **ent-6m** were prepared. 250 μL of each solution were separately diluted with 150 μL water and 100 μL human serum (final concentrations: 10 mM carbocysteine and **ent-6m**, respectively; 20% human serum) and both solutions were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The degradation of both compounds was determined in triplicate right after preparation of the sample (used as a control, 100%), at 2.5 h (elimination half-life of carbocysteine is about 2 h) and after 48 h by UPLC-microTOF-Q (ACQUITY UPLC HSS T3 Column, 1.8 μm , 2.1 x 100 mm). 10 μL of a mixture of 5 μL sample and 600 μL MeOH were injected and eluted with an isocratic method (99:1, H_2O +0.1% formic acid / MeCN, temperature: 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, retention time: 0.7 – 0.8 min).

Methyl (3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-5-oxotetrahydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-3-carboxylate-3-*d* (2)

Compound **1** (500 mg, 2.04 mmol) was reacted with LHMDS (4.0 mL, 4.08 mmol) and purified following the general procedure to afford deuterated compound **2** (427 mg, 1.73 mmol, 85% yield, >95 atom % D) as a yellowish oil. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -127.4 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.0). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₀H₁₄DNNaO₆ 269.0854; Found 269.0857. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 4.76 (dd, *J* = 9.0, 5.9 Hz, 0.04H, H³), 4.30 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H, H²), 4.29 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H, H²), 3.81 (s, 3H, CO₂Me), 3.46 (s, 3H, OMe), 1.57 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.36 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.7 (CO₂Me), 160.8 (C⁵), 107.3 (C⁷), 101.7 (C^{7a}), 66.8 (C²), 59.7 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.2 Hz, C³), 53.0 (CO₂Me), 51.2 (OMe), 16.4 (Me^{7a}), 5.6 (Me⁷).

Methyl (3*R*,7*S*,7*aR*)-7-methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-5-oxotetrahydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-3-carboxylate-3-*d* (ent-2)

Compound **ent-1** (100 mg, 0.408 mmol) was reacted with LHMDS (0.8 mL, 0.816 mmol) and purified following the general procedure to afford deuterated compound **ent-2** (82 mg, 0.334 mmol, 82% yield, 94 atom % D) as a yellowish oil. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +119.9 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.0). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₀H₁₄DNNaO₆ 269.0854; Found 269.0859. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 4.77 (dd, *J* = 9.0, 5.9 Hz, 0.06H, H³), 4.29 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H, H²), 4.13 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H, H²), 3.81 (s, 3H, CO₂Me), 3.46 (s, 3H, OMe), 1.57 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.36 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.7 (CO₂Me), 160.8 (C⁵), 107.3 (C⁷), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 66.7 (C²), 59.7 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.1 Hz, C³), 53.1 (CO₂Me), 51.2 (OMe), 16.3 (Me^{7a}), 15.6 (Me⁷).

L-Serine-2-*d* hydrochloride (3)

Compound **2** (440 mg, 1.79 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general procedure to afford L-Serine-2-*d* hydrochloride **3** (251 mg, 1.77 mmol, 99% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +12.3 (H₂O, *c* 1.0); +9.7 (6 M HCl, *c* 1.0). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₃H₇DNO₃ 107.0561; Found 107.0563. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.17 (dd, *J* = 4.4, 3.5 Hz, 0.04H, H_α), 4.08 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.99 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 1H, H_β). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 170.3 (CO₂H), 59.2 (C_β), 54.5 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.3 Hz, C_α).

D-Serine-2-*d* hydrochloride (**ent-3**)

Compound **ent-2** (50 mg, 0.20 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general procedure to afford D-Serine-2-*d* hydrochloride **ent-3** (28 mg, 0.19 mmol, 96% yield, 91% atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -10.9 (H₂O, *c* 1.0), -8.3 (6 M HCl, *c* 1.0). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₃H₇DNO₃ 107.0561; Found 107.0560. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.20 (dd, *J* = 4.2, 3.7 Hz, 0.09H, H_α), 4.09 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.98 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 1H, H_β). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 170.3 (CO₂H), 59.2 (C_β), 54.5 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.3 Hz, C_α).

N-(9-Fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl)-O-(*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl)-L-serine-2-*d* (**3'**)

Compound **3** (180 mg, 1.25 mmol) and imidazole (170 mg, 2.50 mmol) were dissolved in dry DMF (2 mL) under a nitrogen atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. Then, *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride (TBDMS-Cl) (211 mg, 1.40 mmol) was added, and the mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The solvent was evaporated, and the reaction mixture was dried under vacuum. Hexanes:water (1:1, 3 mL) was added and the suspension was stirred for 1 h, then the mixture was filtered, and the white solid was washed with hexanes. The solid was dried to obtain compound **4**, which was used without further purification (205 mg, 0.93 mmol, yield 74%).

Compound **4** (205 mg, 0.93 mmol), and Na₂CO₃ (158 mg, 1.38 mmol) were dissolved in water (1.6 mL). Dioxane (0.8 mL) was added to the mixture and heated to 37 °C to dissolve the solids. Fmoc-OSu (358 mg, 1.06 mmol) was dissolved in dioxane and transferred to the aqueous solution. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 18 h. The mixture was washed with diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL) and acidified in an ice bath to pH 2 with 1 M HCl to precipitate the amino acid. Then the aqueous phase was extracted with CHCl₃:iPrOH (3 x 15 mL). The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated. The crude mixture was purified by column chromatography with hexanes:ethyl acetate:acetic acid (3:7:0.05) as an eluent to give the final product (compound **3''**) as a white solid (186 mg, 0.42 mmol, yield 45%). mp 102–105 °C. HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M-H]⁻ Calcd for C₂₄H₂₉DNO₅Si 441.1961; Found 441.1959. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 10.10 (br s, 1H, CO₂H), 7.80 (t, 2H, *J*=7.4, 2 CH-Ar), 7.65 (t, 2H, *J*=7.4, 2 CH-Ar), 7.44 (t, 2H, *J*=7.4, 2 CH-Ar), 7.35 (td, 2H, *J*=7.4, 1.3, 2 CH-Ar), 5.69 (br s, 1H, NH), 4.45 (m, 2H, CH₂^{Fmoc}), 4.29 (t, 1H, *J*= 7.3 CH^{Fmoc}), 4.18 (d, 1H, *J*= 10.2, 1CH₂β), 3.93 (d, 1H, *J*= 10.2, 1CH₂β), 0.94 (s, 9H, Si-C(CH₃)₃), 0.12 (s, 3H, Si-CH₃), 0.10 (s, 3H, Si-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 175.7 (CO), 156.1, 143.9, 143.7, 141.3, 141.3 (4C^{Fmoc}), 127.8 (2C, C-Ar), 127.1 (2C, C-Ar), 125.2 (C-Ar), 125.1 (C-Ar), 120.0 (2C, C-Ar), 67.4 (CH₂^{Fmoc}), 63.4 (CH₂β), 47.1 (CH^{Fmoc}), 25.8 (3C, Si-C(CH₃)₃), 18.3 (Si-C(CH₃)₃), -5.5 (2C, Si-(CH₃)₂).

(3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-Methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-3-(((4-methylcoumarin-7-yl)thio)methyl) dihydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-2,5(3*H*)-dione-3-*d* (5a)

Dha **4** (11.0 mg, 0.052 mmol), 7-mercapto-4-methylcoumarin **a** (10.2 mg, 0.053 mmol) and TEA (7.5 μ L, 0.054 mmol) were reacted for 15 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5a** (19.8 mg, 0.049 mmol, 93% yield, 95 atom % D) as a yellow solid. No purification step was needed. mp 62–66 °C. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -51.5 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.00). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₉H₁₈DNO₇SNa 429.0837; Found 429.0833. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 7.56–7.52 (m, 1H, H^{5c}), 7.36–7.33 (m, 2H, H^{6c}, H^{8c}), 6.26 (q, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 1H, H^{3c}), 4.50 (dd, *J* = 10.0, 4.4 Hz, 0.05H, H α), 3.58 (d, *J* = 14.2 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.49 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.22 (d, *J* = 14.2 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.41 (s, 3H, Me^{4c}), 1.66 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.60 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.0 (C²), 160.3 (C^{2c}), 158.6 (C⁵), 153.8 (C^{4c}), 151.9 (C^{8ac}), 139.3 (C^{1c}), 125.1 (C^{8c}, C^{5c}), 118.7 (C^{4ac}), 117.1 (C^{6c}), 114.9 (C^{3c}), 108.3 (C⁷), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 59.7 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.5 Hz, C α), 51.7 (OMe), 34.7 (C β), 22.3 (Me^{7a}), 18.6 (Me^{4c}), 16.7 (Me⁷).

(3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-Methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-3-((tritylthio)methyl)dihydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-2,5(3*H*)-dione-3-*d* (5b)

Dha **4** (50.0 mg, 0.235 mmol), triphenylmethanethiol **b** (64.8 mg, 0.234 mmol) and TEA (33.0 μ L, 0.237 mmol) were reacted for 10 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5b** (115.0 mg, 0.234 mmol, 99% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid after purification by column chromatography (hexanes/ethyl acetate, 7:3). mp 40–42 °C. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -76.4 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.10). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₂₈H₂₆DNO₅SNa 513.1565; Found 513.1559. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 7.51–7.15 (m, 15H, arom.), 4.15 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 4.6 Hz, 0.03H, H α), 3.45 (s, 3H, OMe), 2.74 (d, *J* = 12.9 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.46 (d, *J* = 12.9 Hz, 1H, H β), 1.54 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.44 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.3 (C²), 158.8 (C⁵), 144.1, 129.6, 127.9, 127.1 (3Ph), 107.8 (C⁷), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 67.5 (C δ), 59.4 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.1 Hz, C α), 51.6 (OMe), 33.0 (C β), 21.9 (Me^{7a}), 16.6 (Me⁷).

(3*R*,7*S*,7*aR*)-7-Methoxy-7,7a-dimethyl-3-((tritylthio)methyl)dihydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-2,5(3*H*)-dione-3-*d* (ent-5b)

Dha **ent-4** (54.0 mg, 0.253 mmol), triphenylmethanethiol **b** (70.0 mg, 0.253 mmol) and TEA (35.0 μ L, 0.252 mmol) were reacted for 10 min following the general procedure to give adduct **ent-5b** (108 mg, 0.220 mmol, 87% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid after purification by column chromatography (hexanes/ethyl acetate, 7:3). mp 40–42 $^{\circ}$ C. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +78.8 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.0). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for C₂₈H₂₆DNO₅SNa 513.1565; Found 513.1560. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 7.52–7.16 (m, 15H, arom.), 4.14 (dd, *J* = 11.6, 4.6 Hz, 0.04H, H α), 3.46 (s, 3H, OMe), 2.72 (d, *J* = 12.9 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.45 (d, *J* = 12.9 Hz, 1H, H β), 1.55 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.44 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.4 (C²), 158.8 (C⁵), 144.1, 129.7, 128.2, 127.1 (arom.), 107.9 (C⁷), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 67.5 (C δ), 59.4 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.5 Hz, C α), 51.6 (OMe), 33.0 (C β), 21.9 (Me^{7a}), 16.6 (Me⁷).

(3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-Methoxy-3-(((4-methoxybenzyl)thio)methyl)-7,7a-dimethyl-dihydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazole-2,5(3*H*)-dione-3-*d* (5c)

Dha **4** (30.0 mg, 0.141 mmol), 4-methoxybenzyl mercaptan **c** (64.8 mg, 0.141 mmol) and TEA (20.0 μ L, 0.143 mmol) were reacted for 15 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5c** (47.0 mg, 0.128 mmol, 91% yield, >95 atom % D) as a yellow oil. No purification step was needed. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -41.8 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.00). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for C₁₇H₂₀DNO₆S 369.1225; Found 369.1221. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 7.33–7.22 (m, 2H, H^{2Ph}, H^{6Ph}), 6.88–6.83 (m, 2H, H^{3Ph}, H^{5Ph}), 4.48 (dd, *J* = 9.8, 4.8 Hz, 0.03H, H α), 3.89–3.81 (m, 2H, H δ), 3.80 (s, 3H, OMe^{Ph}), 3.51 (s, 3H, OMe), 2.95 (d, *J* = 14.4 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.66 (d, *J* = 14.4 Hz, 1H, H β),

1.61 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.60 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75z MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.7 (C²), 159.1 (C^{4Ph}), 159.0 (C⁵), 130.4 (C^{2Ph}, C^{6Ph}), 128.9 (C^{1Ph}), 114.2, (C^{3Ph}, C^{5Ph}), 108.3 (C⁷), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 60.6 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 23.1 Hz, C α), 55.4 (OMe^{Ph}), 51.8 (OMe), 35.2 (C δ), 31.5 (C β), 22.2 (Me^{7a}), 16.8 (Me⁷).

(2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*R*,6*S*)-2-(Acetoxymethyl)-6-(((3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-2,5-dioxotetrahydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazol-3-yl-3-*d*)methyl)thio)tetrahydro-2*H*-pyran-3,4,5-triyl triacetate (5d)

Dha **4** (23.0 mg, 0.108 mmol), tetra-*O*-acetyl-1-thio-β-D-glucose **d** (39.3 mg, 0.108 mmol) and TEA (15.2 μL, 0.109 mmol) were reacted for 40 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5d** (62.0 mg, 0.107 mmol, 99% yield, >95 atom % D) as a yellow oil. No purification step was needed. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -78.8 (CHCl₃, *c* 0.98).

HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₂₃H₃₀DNO₁₄SNa 601.1420; Found 601.1423. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 5.23 (t, *J* = 9.4 Hz, 1H, H^{3s}), 5.12–5.00 (m, 2H, H^{2s}, H^{4s}), 4.68 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1H, H^{1s}), 4.60 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 6.5 Hz, 0.04H, H_α), 4.25–4.12 (m, 2H, H^{6s}), 3.71 (ddd, *J* = 10.1, 5.0, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H^{5s}), 3.51 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.16–

3.07 (m, 2H, H_β), 2.06 (s, 3H, OAc), 2.06 (s, 3H, OAc), 2.00 (s, 3H, OAc), 2.01 (s, 3H, OAc), 1.65 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.61 (s, 3H, Me^{7*a*}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 170.6 (C²), 170.1 (CO₂), 170.1 (CO₂), 169.6 (CO₂), 169.4 (CO₂), 158.5 (C⁵), 108.1 (C⁷), 101.4 (C^{7*a*}), 82.5 (C^{1s}), 76.2 (C^{5s}), 73.6 (C^{3s}), 69.6 (C^{2s}), 68.2 (C^{4s}), 62.0 (C^{6s}), 61.0 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.8 Hz, C_α), 51.7 (OMe), 29.9 (C_β), 22.1 (Me^{7*a*}), 20.7 (OAc), 20.7 (OAc), 20.6 (OAc), 20.6 (OAc), 16.6 (Me⁷).

Methyl N-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-S-2-(((3*S*,7*R*,7*aS*)-7-methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-2,5-dioxotetrahydro-5*H*-oxazolo[4,3-*b*]oxazol-3-yl-3-*d*)methyl)-L-cysteinate (5e)

Dha **4** (10.2 mg, 0.048 mmol), Boc-Cys-OMe **e** (11.5 mg, 0.049 mmol) and TEA (7.0 μL, 0.05 mmol) were reacted for 45 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5e** (21.1 mg, 0.047 mmol, 98% yield, 93 atom % D) as a colorless oil. No purification step was needed. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -28.5 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.01).

HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₈H₂₇DN₂O₉SNa 472.1470; Found 472.1472. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 5.43 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, NH), 4.62–4.53 (m, 1H, H_α'), 4.51 (dd, *J* = 10.4, 4.2 Hz, 0.07H, H_α),

3.77 (s, 3H, CO₂Me), 3.51 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.21–3.04 (m, 3H, H_β, H_β'), 2.86 (d, *J* = 14.5 Hz, 1H, H_β), 1.67 (s, 3H, Me⁷), 1.62 (s, 3H, Me^{7*a*}), 1.45 (s, 9H, C(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 171.4 (CO₂Me), 170.4 (C²), 159.0 (C⁵), 155.3 (NHCO₂), 108.4 (C⁷), 101.7 (C^{7*a*}), 80.5 (C(CH₃)₃), 61.3 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 21.7 Hz, C_α), 53.1 (C_α'), 52.9 (CO₂Me), 51.8 (OMe), 34.6 (C_β'), 32.9 (C_β), 28.4 (C(CH₃)₃), 22.3 (Me^{7*a*}), 16.8 (Me⁷).

S-(4-Methylcoumarin-7-yl)-D-cysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (6a)

Compound **5a** (19.0 mg, 0.047 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **6a** (13.1 mg, 0.041 mmol, 87% yield, 93 atom % D) as a yellowish sticky solid. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -27.7 (H₂O, *c* 1.03). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₃H₁₃DNO₄S 281.0701; Found 281.0716. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H, H^{5c}), 7.30 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.7 Hz, 1H, H^{6c}), 7.18 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H, H^{8c}), 6.18 (s, 1H, H^{3c}), 4.27 (dd, *J* = 7.4, 4.2 Hz, 0.07H, H α), 3.72 (d, *J* = 15.1 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.56 (d, *J* = 15.1 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.33 (s, 3H, Me^{4c}). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (75 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 170.2 (CO₂H), 163.5 (C^{2c}), 155.6 (C^{4c}), 152.4 (C^{8ac}), 138.9 (C^{1c}), 125.6 (C^{5c}), 124.9 (C^{6c}), 118.2 (C^{4ac}), 115.7 (C^{8c}), 112.9 (C^{3c}), 51.9 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.5 Hz, C α), 32.4 (C β), 17.8 (Me^{4c}).

D-Cysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (6b)

Compound **5b** (89.0 mg, 0.181 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **6b** (21.0 mg, 0.134 mmol, 74% yield, 95 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -8.1 (6 M HCl, *c* 1.00). MS ESI+ (*m/z*): [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₃H₇DNO₂S 123.03; Found 123.09. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.35 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 4.0 Hz, 0.05H, H α), 3.47 (d, *J* = 15.2 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.28 (d, *J* = 15.1 Hz, 1H, H β). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 171.6 (CO₂H), 36.9 (C β). C α signal was not detected. Around 10% of oxidized D-cystine-2,2'-*d*₂ hydrochloride was also detected by NMR and MS.

L-Cysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (ent-6b)

Compound **ent-5b** (50 mg, 0.102 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **ent-6b** (12.7 mg, 0.081 mmol, 79% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +10.6 (H₂O, *c* 1.00). MS ESI+ (*m/z*): [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₃H₇DNO₂S 123.03; Found 123.09. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.44 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 4.1 Hz, 0.03H, H α), 3.46 (d, *J* = 15.2 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.28 (d, *J* = 15.2 Hz, 1H, H β). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 171.5 (CO₂H), 52.2 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 21.5 Hz, C α), 36.9 (C β).

S-(4-Methoxybenzyl)-D-cysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (6c)

Compound **5c** (13.0 mg, 0.035 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **6c** (8.5 mg, 0.030 mmol, 87% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 20.1$ (6 M HCl, *c* 1.00). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{11}H_{15}DNO_3S$ 243.0908; Found 243.0909. 1H NMR (400 MHz, 4:1 D_2O/CD_3CN) δ (ppm) 7.53–7.48 (m, 2H, arom.), 7.16–7.12 (m, 2H, arom.), 3.98 (OMe), 3.95–3.92 (m, 2H, H δ), 3.16 (d, *J* = 14.7 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.06 (d, *J* = 14.8 Hz, 1H, H β). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, 4:1 D_2O/CD_3CN) δ (ppm) 173.2 (CO₂H), 159.0, 131.2, 115.1 (arom.), 56.2 (OMe), 35.5 (C δ), 32.4 (C β). H α and C α were not detected.

S-(β -D-glucopyranosyl)-D-cysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (6d)

Compound **5d** (58.6 mg, 0.101 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **6d** (30.9 mg, 0.096 mmol, 95% yield, >95 atom % D) as a colourless syrup. $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 9.0$ (H_2O , *c* 1.00). 1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 4.61 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H, H^{1s}), 4.40 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 4.0 Hz, 0.05H, H α), 3.93 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H, H^{6s}), 3.70 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 6.3 Hz, 1H, H^{6s}), 3.56–3.27 (m, 6H, H β , H^{2s}, H^{3s}, H^{4s}, H^{5s}). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 170.4 (CO₂H), 85.8 (C^{1s}), 79.8 (C^{5s}), 76.9 (C^{3s}), 72.0 (C^{4s}), 69.3 (C^{2s}), 60.8 (C^{6s}), 52.8 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 20.6 Hz, C α), 30.9 (C β).

S-((*R*)-2'-amino-2'-carboxyethyl)-D-cysteine-2-*d* dihydrochloride (6e)

Compound **5e** (15.5 mg, 0.034 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **6e** (9.0 mg, 0.032 mmol, 93% yield, 90 atom % D) as a colourless syrup. 1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 4.45 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 4.2 Hz, 0.10H, H α), 4.33 (dd, *J* = 6.7, 4.7 Hz, 1H, H α'), 3.36–3.09 (m, 4H, H β , H β'). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 170.4 (2 CO₂H), 52.2 (C α'), 52.0 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 19.6 Hz, C α), 31.6 (C β'), 31.5 (C β).

(R)-2-Amino-3-(benzylamino)propanoic-2-d acid hydrochloride (6f)

Dha **4** (21.0 mg, 0.10 mmol) and benzylamine (10.9 μ L, 0.10 mmol) were reacted for 40 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5f** (75% conversion, 93 atom % D). HRMS ESI+ (m/z) for **5f** extracted from the crude mixture: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{16}H_{20}DN_2O_5$ 322.1508; Found 322.1506. NMR data for **5f** extracted from the crude mixture: 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 7.37–7.22 (m, 5H, arom.), 4.55 (dd, $J = 8.4$, 4.8 Hz, 0.07H, H_α), 3.97–3.80 (m, 2H, H_δ), 3.50 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.15 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.01 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 1.63 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}), 1.61 (s, 3H, Me^7). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 176.3 (C^2), 171.1 (C^5), 139.2, 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 127.5, 127.4 (arom.), 108.6 (C^7), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 52.8 (C_δ), 51.8 (OMe), 48.5 (C_β), 22.1 (Me^{7a}), 16.8 (Me^7). C_α was not detected.

The crude mixture was the hydrolysed and purified following the general procedure to afford compound **6f** (19.4 mg, 0.084 mmol, 88% global yield, 88 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 $^\circ C$ (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -19.6 (H_2O , c 1.00). HRMS (ESI) m/z : $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{10}H_{14}DN_2O_2$ 196.1191; Found 196.1194. 1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 7.57–7.43 (m, 5H, arom.), 4.43–4.33 (m, 2H, H_δ), 4.30 (dd, $J = 8.6$, 5.6 Hz, 0.12H, H_α), 3.63 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.54 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 169.7 (CO_2H), 130.2, 130.1, 129.6, 129.4, 129.0 (arom.), 52.0 (C_δ), 48.9 (t, $J_{C-D} = 22.2$ Hz, C_α), 45.3 (C_β).

(S)-2-Amino-3-(benzylamino)propanoic-2-d acid hydrochloride (ent-6f)

Dha **ent-4** (21.0 mg, 0.10 mmol) and benzylamine (10.9 μ L, 0.10 mmol) were reacted for 40 min following the general procedure to give adduct **ent-5f**, which was directly hydrolysed and purified following the general procedure to afford compound **ent-6f** (18.3 mg, 0.079 mmol, 80% global yield, 92 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 $^\circ C$ (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +16.5 (H_2O , c 1.00). HRMS (ESI) m/z : $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{10}H_{14}DN_2O_2$ 196.1191; Found 196.1187. 1H NMR (300 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 7.61–7.46 (m, 5H, arom.), 4.48–4.30 (s, 2H, $PhCH_2$), 4.06 (dd, $J = 8.3$, 6.4 Hz, 0.08H, H_α), 3.60–3.40 (br s, 2H, H_β). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (75 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 170.6 (CO_2H), 130.0, 129.8, 129.7, 129.3, 129.3 (arom.), 51.4 ($PhCH_2$), 48.7 (t, $J_{C-D} = 21.7$ Hz, C^α), 45.2 (C^β).

6h

The crude mixture was the hydrolysed and purified following the general procedure to afford compound **6h** (17.2 mg, 0.088 mmol, 89% global yield, 91 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -27.7 (H₂O, *c* 1.00). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for C₇H₁₄DN₂O₂ 160.1190; Found 160.1188. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.42 (dd, *J* = 9.1, 4.9 Hz, 0.09H, H α), 3.93–3.78 (m, 3H, H β , H δ), 3.61 (d, *J* = 13.4 Hz, 1H, H β), 3.30–3.17 (m, 2H, H¹), 2.26–2.02 (m, 4H, H ϵ). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 169.3 (CO₂H), 56.4 (C δ), 54.6 (C δ), 53.2 (C β), 48.6 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.5 Hz, C α), 22.8 (C ϵ), 22.7 (C ϵ).

(R)-2-Amino-3-(piperidin-1-yl)propanoic-2-*d* acid hydrochloride (6i)

5i

Dha **4** (21.0 mg, 0.10 mmol) and piperidine (10.0 μ L, 0.10 mmol) were reacted for 10 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5i** (>95% conversion, 94 atom % D). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -83.8 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.02). HRMS ESI+ (*m/z*) for **5i** extracted from the crude mixture: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for C₁₄H₂₂DN₂O₅ 300.1664; Found 300.1666. NMR data for **5i** extracted from the crude mixture: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 4.48 (dd, *J* = 7.2, 3.6 Hz, 0.06H, H α), 3.48 (s, 3H, OMe), 2.92 (d, *J* = 14.1 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.83 (d, *J* = 14.0 Hz, 1H, H β), 2.60–2.53 (m, 4H, H δ), 1.69 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}), 1.60–1.51 (m, 7H, Me⁷, H ϵ), 1.46–1.36 (m, 2H, H ζ). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 171.8 (C²), 159.1 (C⁵), 108.1 (C⁷), 101.7 (C^{7a}), 60.3 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.2 Hz, C α), 59.1 (C β), 54.7 (C δ), 51.7 (OMe), 25.9 (C ϵ), 24.0 (C ζ), 22.0 (Me^{7a}), 16.8 (Me⁷).

6i

The crude mixture was the hydrolysed and purified following the general procedure to afford compound **6i** (19.2 mg, 0.092 mmol, 93% global yield, 89 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 °C (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -24.7 (H₂O, *c* 1.00). HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for C₈H₁₆DN₂O₂ 174.1347; Found 174.1345. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 4.39 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 5.9 Hz, 0.11H, H α), 3.80–3.56 (m, 4H, H β , H δ), 3.21–3.02 (m, 2H, H δ), 2.06–1.90 (m, 2H, H ϵ), 1.89–1.70 (m, 3H, H ϵ , H δ), 1.61–1.45 (m, 1H, H ζ). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm) 169.9 (CO₂H), 55.2 (C β), 54.9 (C¹), 53.6 (C δ), 47.6 (t, *J*_{C-D} = 22.8 Hz, C α), 22.8 (C ϵ), 20.8 (C ζ).

(R)-2-Amino-3-(azepan-1-yl)propanoic-2-d acid hydrochloride (6j)

Dha **4** (21.0 mg, 0.10 mmol) and azepane (11.5 μ L, 0.10 mmol) were reacted for 20 min following the general procedure to give adduct **5j** (93% conversion, 93 atom % D). HRMS ESI+ (m/z) for **5j** extracted from the crude mixture: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{15}H_{24}DN_2O_5$ 314.1820; Found 314.1822. NMR data for **5j** extracted from the crude mixture: 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 4.47 (dd, $J = 7.8, 3.7$ Hz, 0.07H, H_α), 3.49 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.16 (d, $J = 14.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.03 (d, $J = 14.2$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 2.86–2.80 (m, 4H, H_δ), 1.70–1.53 (m, 14H, Me^7 , Me^{7a} , H_ζ , H_ϵ).

$^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 171.9 (C^2), 159.2 (C^5), 108.2 (C^7), 101.7 (C^{7a}), 60.4 (t, $J_{C-D} = 22.3$ Hz, C_α), 57.9 (C_β), 55.3 (C_δ), 51.7 (OMe), 28.2 (C_ϵ), 27.1 (C_ζ), 22.0 (Me^{7a}), 16.8 (Me^7).

The crude mixture was hydrolysed and purified following the general procedure to afford compound **6j** (19.6 mg, 0.088 mmol, 89% global yield, 88 atom % D) as a white solid. mp 230–240 $^\circ C$ (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -21.1 (H_2O , c 1.00). HRMS (ESI) m/z: $[M+H]^+$ Calcd for $C_9H_{18}DN_2O_2$ 188.1504; Found 188.1504. 1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 4.41 (dd, $J = 8.6, 5.7$ Hz, 0.12H, H_α), 3.77–3.52 (m, 2H, H_δ), 3.47–3.26 (m, 2H, H_δ), 2.04–1.82 (m, 4H, H_ϵ), 1.80–1.54 (m, 4H, H_ζ). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 169.9 (CO_2H), 55.4 (C^1), 55.3 (C_β), 54.8 (C_δ), 47.7 (t, $J_{C-D} = 22.1$ Hz, C_α), 25.8

(C_ϵ), 23.4 (C_ζ).

(3R,7S,7aR)-7-Methoxy-7,7a-dimethyl-3-((phenylselanyl)methyl)dihydro-5H-oxazolo[4,3-b]oxazole-2,5(3H)-dione-3-d (ent-5k)

Dha **ent-4** (21.0 mg, 0.098 mmol) and diphenyl diselenide **k** (20.5 mg, 0.070 mmol) were reacted for 5 min following the general procedure to give adduct **ent-5k** (27.0 mg, 0.073 mmol, 74% yield, >95 atom % D) as a white solid after purification by column chromatography. mp 86–88 $^\circ C$. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +22.6 ($CHCl_3$, c 1.03). HRMS (ESI) m/z: $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{15}H_{16}DNO_5SeNa$ 395.0027; Found 395.0230. 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 7.70–7.65 (m, 2H, arom.), 7.33–7.29 (m, 3H, arom.), 4.52 (dd, $J = 11.2, 4.4$ Hz, 0.04H, H_α), 3.47 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.38

(d, $J = 13.1$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 3.05 (d, $J = 13.1$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 1.59 (s, 3H, Me^7), 1.57 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) 170.7 (CO_2), 158.9 (NCO_2), 134.9, 129.5, 128.4, 128.2 (arom.), 108.0 (C^7), 101.6 (C^{7a}), 60.9 (t, $J_{C-D} = 22.0$ Hz, C_α), 51.7 (OMe), 28.3 (C_β), 22.2 (Me^{7a}), 16.8 (Me^7).

Methyl 2-((((3*R*,7*S*,7*aR*)-7-methoxy-7,7*a*-dimethyl-2,5-dioxotetrahydro-5*H*-oxazol[4,3-*b*]oxazol-3-yl-3-*d*)methylthio)acetate (ent-5m)

ent-5m

Dha **ent-4** (54.2 mg, 0.254 mmol), methyl thioglycolate **f** (27.0 mg, 0.254 mmol) and TEA (38.0 μ L, 0.273 mmol) were reacted for 20 min following the general procedure to give adduct **ent-5m** (80.4 mg, 0.251 mmol, 99% yield, >95 atom % D) as a yellowish oil. No purification step was needed. $[\alpha]_D^{20} +86.7$ (CHCl_3 , c 1.00). HRMS (ESI) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{DNNO}_7\text{S}$ 343.0681; Found 343.0680. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) 4.58 (dd, $J = 10.5, 4.4$ Hz, 0.03H, H_α), 3.74 (s, 3H, CO_2Me), 3.49 (s, 3H, OMe), 3.46–3.35 (m, H_δ), 3.22 (d, $J = 14.5$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 2.96 (d, $J = 14.5$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 1.65 (s, 3H, Me^7), 1.61 (s, 3H, Me^{7a}). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) 16.7 (Me^7), 170.4 (CO_2Me), 170.4 (C^2), 159.0 (C^5), 108.3 (C^7), 101.7 (C^{7a}), 60.7 (t, $J_{\text{C-D}} = 22.9$ Hz, C_α), 52.6 (CO_2Me), 51.8 (OMe), 32.4 (C_δ), 32.3 (C_β), 22.2 (Me^{7a}).

Carbocysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (ent-6m)

ent-6m

Compound **ent-5m** (81.4 mg, 0.254 mmol) was hydrolyzed and purified following the general protocol to afford deuterated derivative **ent-6m** (50.1 mg, 0.231 mmol, 91% yield, 93 atom % D) as a light pale brownish solid. mp 230–240 $^\circ\text{C}$ (dec.). $[\alpha]_D^{20} -34.2$ (H_2O , c 1.00). HRMS (ESI) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{DNO}_4\text{S}$ 181.0388; Found 181.0396. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 4.17 (dd, $J = 7.8, 4.5$ Hz, 0.07H, H_α), 3.32 (s, 2H, H_δ), 3.13 (d, $J = 15.1$ Hz, 1H, H_β), 2.98 (d, $J = 15.1$ Hz, 1H, H_β). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 174.0 (C_ϵ), 170.0 (CO_2H), 51.7 (t, $J_{\text{C-D}} = 22.2$ Hz, C_α), 33.8 (C_δ), 31.8 (C_β).

Scaled-up synthesis of carbocysteine-2-*d* hydrochloride (ent-6m)

Chiral bicyclic Dha **ent-4** (500 mg, 2.345 mmol) was dissolved in a 9:1 mixture of 2-propanol-OD ($^i\text{PrOD}$) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (25 mL) in a Schlenk under Ar atmosphere. Then, methyl thioglycolate **f** (249 mg, 2.346 mmol) and TEA (330 μ L, 2.368 mmol) were added, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The solution was dried under vacuum, the resulting oil was suspended in an aqueous 6 M HCl solution (100 mL), and the mixture was refluxed in an oil bath for 16 h. The solvent was then removed under vacuum and the crude mixture was redissolved in water (50 mL) and washed thrice with ethyl acetate (50 mL). The aqueous phase was concentrated, and the crude mixture was purified by solid phase extraction in a C18 cartridge to afford deuterated derivative **ent-6m** (445 mg, 2.064 mmol, 88% yield, 93 atom % D) as a light pale brownish solid.

3. Copies of the NMR spectra for all new compounds

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in CDCl_3 (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

HSQC in CDCl₃ (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in 4:1 $\text{D}_2\text{O}/\text{CD}_3\text{CN}$ (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in 4:1 $\text{D}_2\text{O}/\text{CD}_3\text{CN}$ (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in 4:1 D₂O/CD₃CN (298 K)

HSQC in 4:1 D₂O/CD₃CN (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (300 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (75 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

^1H NMR in D_2O (400 MHz, 298 K)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR in D_2O (100 MHz, 298 K)

COSY in D₂O (298 K)

HSQC in D₂O (298 K)

4. Copies of the 2D-NOESY NMR spectra

NOESY in CDCl₃ (298 K)

5. HRMS spectra and HPLC chromatograms of peptides

Peptide myr-Src

Myr-Gly1-Ser2-Asn3-Lys4-Ser5-Lys6-Pro7-Lys8-Asp9-Ala10-Ser11-Gln12

HRMS (ESI+) m/z: calcd. for C₆₄H₁₁₆N₁₈O₂₀: [M+2H]²⁺: 728.4301 found: 728.4311.

Semi-preparative HPLC: Rt = 14.47 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (30:70) → (37.5:62.5), 15 min, 20 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Analytical HPLC: Rt = 9.03 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (35:65) → (50:50), 15 min, 1 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Peptide **myr-Src (Ser^{D2})**

Myr-Gly1-Ser^{D2}-Asn3-Lys4-Ser5-Lys6-Pro7-Lys8-Asp9-Ala10-Ser11-Gln12

HRMS (ESI+) m/z: calcd. for C₆₄H₁₁₅DN₁₈O₂₀: [M+2H]²⁺: 728.9333 found: 728.9331.

Semi-preparative HPLC: Rt = 14.47 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (30:70) → (37.5:62.5), 15 min, 20 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Analytical HPLC: Rt = 9.03 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (35:65) → (50:50), 15 min, 1 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Peptide **myr-Src (Ser^{D5})**

Myr-Gly1-Ser2-Asn3-Lys4-Ser^{D5}-Lys6-Pro7-Lys8-Asp9-Ala10-Ser11-Gln12

HRMS (ESI+) m/z: calcd. for C₆₄H₁₁₅DN₁₈O₂₀: [M+2H]²⁺: 728.9333 found: 728.9338.

Semi-preparative HPLC: Rt = 14.47 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (30:70) → (37.5:62.5), 15 min, 20 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Analytical HPLC: Rt = 9.03 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (35:65) → (50:50), 15 min, 1 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Peptide **myr-Src (Ser^{D11})**

Myr-Gly1-Ser2-Asn3-Lys4-Ser5-Lys6-Pro7-Lys8-Asp9-Ala10-Ser^{D11}-Gln12

HRMS (ESI+) m/z: calcd. for C₆₄H₁₁₅DN₁₈O₂₀: [M+2H]²⁺: 728.9333 found: 728.9336.

Semi-preparative HPLC: Rt = 14.47 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (30:70) → (37.5:62.5), 15 min, 20 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Analytical HPLC: Rt = 9.03 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (35:65) → (50:50), 15 min, 1 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Peptide myr-Src (Ser^{D2}, 5, 11)

Myr-Gly1-Ser^{D2}-Asn3-Lys4-Ser^{D5}-Lys6-Pro7-Lys8-Asp9-Ala10-Ser^{D11}-Gln12

HRMS (ESI+) m/z: calcd. for C₆₄H₁₁₃D₃N₁₈O₂₀: [M+2H]²⁺: 729.9395 found: 729.9384.

Semi-preparative HPLC: Rt = 14.47 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (30:70) → (37.5:62.5), 15 min, 20 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

Analytical HPLC: Rt = 9.03 min, (gradient: acetonitrile/water+0.1% TFA (35:65) → (50:50), 15 min, 1 mL/min λ = 212 nm).

